

Some Ligand Substitution Reactions in Oxo-Molybdenum (V) Chelates. Part V

R. L. Dutta* and B. Chatterjee

Bidentate, heterocyclic ligands (YY), such as *o*-phenanthroline, $\alpha\alpha'$ -dipyridyl, 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline and 2,9-dimethyl-*o*-phenanthroline react under reflux with oxo-molybdenum (V) complexes $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{X})(\text{AB})]_2$ to provide $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{AB})(\text{YY})\text{MoO}_2(\text{AB})]$, (where X = pyridine or picolines, AB = picolinic acid, quinaldinic acid, 8-hydroxyquinoline or substituted 8-hydroxyquinolines). The complexes have molybdenum in +5 state, provide usual infra red bands for Mo = O but their reflectance spectra are not sufficiently resolved to reveal the ligand field bands. The complexes are all diamagnetic.

Of the many types of oxo-molybdenum (V) complexes that we had earlier described¹ with inner metallic ligands, one unique type was $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{X})(\text{AB})]$ (where X = pyridine, picolines, thiourea etc. and AB = pyridine/quinoline carboxylic acid or 8-hydroxyquinolines). These complexes were all obtained in shining crystalline form, provided a +5 oxidation state for molybdenum and were diamagnetic or nearly so (Table I). This last property indicated a substantial dimerisation, so that the following structures were tentatively suggested :

When two molybdenum (V) octahedra share an edge through two bridging oxygens, the X groups in the two octahedra occupy relatively *cis* positions. It occurred to us, therefore, that in the event of the two X groups occupying *cis* dispositions, it may not be quite unreasonable to attempt replacing the two *cis* 'X's by a bidentate, strongfield heterocycle. With this end in view four heterocycles, namely *o*-phenanthroline, α , α' -dipyridyl, 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline and 2,9-dimethyl-*o*-phenanthroline were used for these ligands substitution reactions. The selected complexes were those with X being pyridine or β -picoline and AB being quinaldinic acid, 8-hydroxyquinolic or its bromo substituted derivative. In all cases refluxing the complexes with the heterocyclic bases in spirit for some hours brought about complete substitution and provided the complexes $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{AB})(\text{YY})\text{MoO}_2(\text{AB})]$ in quite crystalline form.

Besides analysing the molybdenum and nitrogen content of the complexes, the α, α' -dipyridyl bridged complex was also analysed quantitatively for dipyridyl by decomposing the complex in alkaline medium, extracting dipyridyl with chloroform and then measuring spectrophotometrically.

* Present address—Department of Chemistry, Ohio State University, U.S.A.

1. R. L. Dutta and B. Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 759.

The complexes provide +5 oxidation state for the molybdenum and gave diamagnetic values (vide Table I). The diamagnetic values suggested dimeric behaviour and a smooth substitution reaction. The reflectance spectra of two of the samples were obtained but unfortunately the spectra were not sufficiently resolved to allow the identification of the ligand field bands separately from the intense charge transfer bands.

TABLE I

Physical properties of the complexes

Compound	Colour	Oxidation state	eff (B.M.)*
[Mo ₂ O ₄ Q ₂ (<i>o</i> -Phen)]	Orange	5.1	Diamagnetic
[Mo ₂ O ₄ Q ₂ (dipy)]	„	5.1	„
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (DBO) ₂ (<i>o</i> -phen)]	Brown	Not determined	„
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (oxine) ₂ (<i>o</i> -Phen)]	Maroon	„	„
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (oxine) ₂ (dipy)]	„	„	„
[Mo ₂ O ₄ Q ₂ (5-nitro- <i>o</i> -phen)]	Orange	4.9	„
[Mo ₂ O ₄ Q ₂ (2,9-dimethyl- <i>o</i> -phen)]	„	5.0	„

(QH = quinaldinic acid, *o*-phen = *o*-phenanthroline; dipy = α, α' -dipyridyl, DBO = 5,7-dibromo oxine, 5-nitro-*o*-phen = 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline, and 2,9-dimethyl-*o*-phen = 2,9-dimethyl *o*-phenanthroline)

* Calculated from $\lambda_{M.c.o.r.}$ using Curie equation $\mu_{eff} = (\lambda_{M.c.o.r.} \times T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

Representative members of this series revealed the molybdenyl bands in the infra red around 950–955 cm⁻¹.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ammonium oxo-pentachloromolybdate (V) (*emerald green*) was prepared by following standard procedure². All refluxing was done on a sand bath.

1. μ -*o*-phenanthroline-tetraoxo-bis(quinaldinato)-dimolybdenum (V) (*orange*): Pyridine-dioxo-mono quinaldinato-molybdenum (V) (*red*) was prepared by a procedure described earlier¹. The compound was washed repeatedly with spirit and sucked dry. The dry compound (0.62 g) was suspended in spirit (15.0 ml.) and *o*-phenanthroline (0.18 g.) in 5 ml. rectified spirit was added to it and refluxed for 1 hour. The product was cooled, filtered and washed several times with rectified spirit and finally dried over CaCl₂. Found: Mo, 24.9%; N, 7.7%. [Mo₂O₄Q₂ (*o*-phen)] requires: Mo, 24.6%; N, 7.2%.

The same compound was also synthesised from β -picoline-dioxo-monoquinaldinato-molybdenum (V) (*red*) by following the above procedure. Found: Mo, 25.0%; N, 7.6%.

2. μ - α, α' -dipyridyl-tetraoxo-bis(quinaldinato)-dimolybdenum (V) (*orange*) was obtained from pyridine-dioxo-mono quinaldinato-molybdenum (V) (*red*) (0.55 g) by following the above procedure using α, α' -dipyridyl (0.15 g) in place of *o*-phenanthroline. Found: Mo, 25.8%; N, 7.7%. [Mo₂O₄Q₂(dipy)] requires: Mo, 25.3%; N, 7.4%; 0.044 g. of the sample gave 0.0084 g. dipyridyl: required 0.009 g..

3. μ -*o*-phenanthroline-tetraoxo-bis(dibromooxinato)-dimolybdenum (V) (brown) : Pyridine-dioxo-monodibromooxinato-molybdenum (V) (orange-brown) was synthesised as described earlier³ of this series. The freshly prepared compound (0.85 g.) was suspended in rectified spirit (20.0 ml.). *o*-phenanthroline (0.18 g) in 10 ml. spirit was added to it and refluxed for 6 hrs. The product was cooled, filtered, washed several times with spirit and dried over CaCl₂. Found : Mo, 19.22%; N, 5.3%; Br, 30.3%. [Mo₂O₄(DBO)₂(*o*-phen)] requires : Mo, 18.4%; N, 5.3%; Br, 30.7%.

4. μ -*o*-phenanthroline-tetraoxo-bis (oxinato)-dimolybdenum (V) (maroon) was prepared from pyridine-dioxo-mono oxinato molybdenum (V) (orange) by refluxing with calculated amount of *o*-phenanthroline in spirit for 3 hrs. It was cooled, filtered, washed several times with spirit and dried over CaCl₂. Found : Mo, 27.0%; N, 7.2%. [Mo₂O₄(oxine)₂(*o*-phen)] requires : Mo, 26.2%; N, 7.7%.

5. μ - α, α' -dipyridyl-tetraoxo-bis (oxinato)-dimolybdenum (V) (maroon) was prepared as above using α, α' -dipyridyl in place of *o*-phenanthroline. Found : Mo, 27.8%; N, 7.8%; [Mo₂O₄(oxine)₂(dipy)] requires : Mo, 27.3%; N, 8.0%; 0.050 g. of the sample gave 0.0108 g. dipyridyl; Required, 0.01114 g.

6. μ -5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline-tetraoxo-bis(quinaldinato)-dimolybdenum (V) (orange) was obtained as above using 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline in place of *o*-phenanthroline. Found : Mo, 22.8%; N, 9.0%. [Mo₂O₄Q₂(5-nitro-*o*-phen)] requires : Mo, 23.2%; N, 8.48%.

7. μ -2,9-dimethyl-*o*-phenanthroline-tetraoxo-bis(quinaldinato)-dimolybdenum (V) (orange) was obtained as above using 2,9-dimethyl *o*-phenanthroline in place of 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline. Found : Mo, 23.2%; N, 6.5%. [Mo₂O₄Q₂(2,9-dimethyl *o*-phen)] requires : Mo, 23.9%; N, 6.9%.

Analytical Methods : Molybdenum content was determined either (a) by decomposing the complex with equal volumes of conc. H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ and then after adjusting the pH, molybdenum was precipitated with oxine. The precipitate was re-dissolved in hot alkali, reprecipitated with dilute H₂SO₄, dried and weighed as [MoO₂(oxine)₂]. Alternatively the complex was decomposed with alkali-hydrogen peroxide and molybdenum was precipitated with oxine after adjusting to suitable pH, reprecipitating as above and finally weighing as [MoO₂(oxine)₂]. In case of latter method of estimation of Mo, same procedure as in Part IV³ of this series was followed.

Estimation of ring-substituted bromine was made by decomposing the complex with alkali-hydrogen peroxide, molybdenum was then removed as oxinate and bromide precipitated as AgBr. This was filtered, dissolved in ammonia and reprecipitated with dilute HNO₃ and finally weighed as AgBr.

Nitrogen was estimated by semi-micro combustion technique. In a few cases, as in [Mo₂O₄Q₂(dipy)] and [Mo₂O₄(oxine)₂(dipy)], the ligand, dipyridyl was estimated by refluxing the complex with 0.2N NaOH and then extracting with A. R. Chloroform and finally measuring spectrophotometrically. This estimation was run as a check because starting pyridine complex and the resulting dipyridyl complex have similar analytical figures of Mo and N.

3. R. L. Dutta and B. Chatterjee, "Molybdenum Part IV", *this journal*, under publication.

Oxidation state of molybdenum in the complex was determined by dissolving a known weight of the complex under magnetic stirring (which sometimes needed more than an hour) in excess acidified ferric alum and finally titrating the ferrous ion found in solution.

The determination of oxidation state of $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Q}_2(\text{dipy})]$ was considered here as a representative example :

Complex, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Q}_2(\text{dipy})]$ (0.0800 gm.) was stirred in a stoppered flask with an excess acidified ferric alum solution (75 ml. ferric alum solution and 25.0 ml. 2*N* H_2SO_4). After dissolution, it was cooled in ice and added A.R. syrupy phosphoric acid (5.0 ml.). It was then titrated immediately with KMnO_4 (0.03686 *N*) to a first pink colour. Volume of KMnO_4 consumed = 6.0 ml. Blank containing 0.0364 gm. quinaldinic acid and 0.03301 gm. dipyrityl and finally diluted to 100 ml. (25.0 ml. 2*N* H_2SO_4 and 75.0 ml. distilled water) consumed = 0.1 ml. KMnO_4 . Total volume of KMnO_4 (0.03686 *N*) required = 5.9 ml. %Mo = $5.9 \times 0.03686 \times 0.096 \times 100 / 0.0800 = 26.16$; 1 ml. of (*N*) $\text{KMnO}_4 = 0.096$ gm. Mo.

Magnetic Measurements : The magnetic susceptibilities were determined by the Gouy method using a semi micro Mettler Balance for measuring the difference in weight with a field strength of 8.44×10^3 gauss. Diamagnetic corrections were taken from Selwood⁴. Recrystallised copper sulphate pentahydrate was used as calibrant.

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Inorganic Chemistry Laboratory,
The University of Burdwan,
Burdwan, West Bengal.

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